

SUHAMK COARAB PROJECT: PILOTING

Piloting the new Qualitative Researcher Evaluation
Criteria at Häme University of Applied Sciences
(HAMK).

Abstract

The new qualitative researcher criteria was developed as part of the SuHAMK CoARAb project and were tested in three pilots at Häme University of Applied Sciences. This document contains the detailed description of the piloting process, results and feedback from these three pilots.

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Introduction

SuHAMK CoARAb Project

This document has been created as part of the SuHAMK CoARAb project at Häme University of Applied Sciences. The SuHAMK CoARAb project is part of the CoARA Cascade Boost Funding and funded by the European Union.

This 1-year EU funded project aims to develop new effective qualitative researcher evaluation criteria which will be mapped into HAMK's existing principal research scientist evaluation processes. The new qualitative researcher evaluation criteria support the recognition of diverse researcher skills and different researcher career paths, enhances HAMK's research quality and promotes transparency and accountability in the researcher evaluation processes. Strong collaboration with HAMK's principal research scientists, principal research scientist supervisors, the researcher evaluation team and other relevant HAMK personnel have helped identify the new qualitative evaluation criteria in this document. A new sustainable evaluation framework will be developed around these new criteria and comprehensive training on their active utilization will be provided to relevant HAMK personnel.

Piloting Process

In total **3 pilots** were conducted. **Two** of the **pilots** used the new qualitative evaluation criteria during an **external recruitment** process for **new Principal Research Scientists**. **One** of **pilots** was an **internal recruitment** where an existing **lecturer at HAMK**, had requested an **evaluation to become a Principal Research Scientist**.

External Recruitment Pilots

In the external recruitment pilots, two different supervisors were responsible for igniting the recruitment process and conducting the initial evaluations, performing interviews and choosing the final candidates. After the final candidates were chosen, the HR team were involved in the final 'tenure track evaluation' process, in which it was decided if the candidate would automatically become a Principal Research Scientists, or if they needed to be first placed on the tenure track path.

Each supervisor conducted the initial evaluation and interview process quite differently and utilized the new criteria to a differing extent. The issue of uniformity in the recruitment of Principal Research Scientist has already been identified as a critical development need. However, as new recruitment guidelines and processes have not yet been secured, we needed to allow the supervisors to perform the recruitment in the manner they had already been accustomed to. This also provided an important opportunity to observe how different supervisors conduct the recruitment and evaluation of potential candidates and better

understand best practices and potential issues supervisors may face when using the new qualitative evaluation criteria.

Internal Recruitment Pilot

In the internal recruitment pilot, the candidate had requested to be considered for the Principal Research Scientist position. One supervisor had already performed the initial evaluation to confirm the candidate's competence for the Principal Research Scientist position. For this evaluation the new qualitative evaluation criteria were not utilized. However, once the candidate was confirmed as competent for the Principal Research Scientist position, the tenure track evaluation was completed to confirm if the candidate would automatically become a Principal Research Scientists, or if they needed to be first placed on the tenure track path. Similarly, the HR team were heavily involved in this process and the new qualitative researcher evaluation criteria were incorporated into this process.

External Pilots

External Pilot 1

Personnel responsible:
Researcher Supervisor, HAMK Edu research unit.

Applications received:
3

Recruitment process followed:
Principal Research Scientist job notification published on Kuntarekry. The supervisor responsible created the job notification, decided upon the roles and duties, the contract type, salary and other important aspects.
<i>"After publication of the job notification all the applications were read twice and three best were selected to face to face interview. After the interview candidate number 1 was so clear to be selected that no further interview rounds were not needed. After the interview the applicant was tested by Eezy and the final decision was made together with vice-rector and research and innovation -director. There are very seldom applicants to our principal research scientist positions, who are assistant professors and at the same time have very good experience in working in companies/with companies."</i>

Qualitative researcher evaluation criteria tested and at which stage:
<i>"All the criteria were used. Before the interviews the criteria were compared with the written materials and during the interview the missing information was tried to monitor."</i>

On what merits were the candidates chosen:

“Almost all.”

Feedback:**Positives:**

Almost all the relevant criteria was covered.

Challenges:

The criteria was quite heavy and maybe too detailed. Some parts of the criteria repeated the other ones. The “title” -level worked quite well also in interview -situation.

Improvement suggestions:

Because we are so dependent on the external and competed RDI -funding, maybe it could be highlighted more and could even be one own sub criteria.

Which qualitative criteria would you suggest adopting:

Multiple.

Any other comments:

Thanks for your work!

External Pilot 2

Personnel responsible:

Researcher Supervisor, HAMK Bio research unit.

Applications received:

46

Recruitment process followed:

Applicants were asked to complete an application form, to which a CV and a research plan were attached.

I reviewed all the applications. I invited four applicants to 45-minute Teams interviews. The interviewees were the Head of the Research Unit and the Director of Research and

Innovation. Two applicants were invited to Hämeenlinna for an interview and to familiarize themselves with the laboratories and potential future colleagues.

After the two best applicants had been selected and I had decided to hire both, I discussed the matter further with HR. I carried out the tenure track evaluations and discussed the candidates with Heidi Ahokallio-Leppälä. After that, I informed the applicants that they had been selected.

Qualitative researcher evaluation criteria tested and at which stage:

The criteria were, in principle, used at every stage of the recruitment process. However, during the review of the applications, they were not examined systematically. Shortlisting from 46 applications is labor-intensive, and at that stage it is not possible to reflect each application against the criteria in detail.

During the interviews, questions related to the criteria were asked, but the criteria were not reviewed point by point. However, the Head of the Research Unit had familiarized herself with the criteria prior to the interviews. The interviews also included questions that were not related to the criteria.

The criteria were used most systematically when conducting the tenure track evaluations for the selected candidates. At that stage, all the criteria were reviewed.

On what merits were the candidates chosen:

Because the recruited individuals will primarily be leading their own research groups, the criteria emphasized research competence rather than teaching competence. Both selected candidates were accomplished researchers who were appointed directly to Principal Research Scientist positions without a tenure track period. This means that they were at a high level across all the criteria. In the selection process, I placed particular emphasis on:

- Peer-reviewed publications
- Relevant research experience
- Experience in applied research
- Funding applications

Feedback:

Positives:

It is good that such criteria are being developed at HAMK. This makes PRS recruitment more transparent and equitable. The criteria help assess whether a person should be hired with a PRH title in the first place, or whether, for example, a postdoctoral researcher position would be more suitable for a less experienced applicant. They also make it possible to evaluate the stage of a person's career. In addition, the criteria help ensure a more equitable salary level.

Challenges:

What makes the use of the criteria challenging is that there are a great many of them, and each criterion includes several different aspects to be assessed, many of which are quite overlapping. Another challenge was that the process was still in the development phase, so new information and expectations emerged along the way. For example, it was not known in advance that tenure track evaluations would need to be carried out for the selected individuals. Even now, it is not entirely clear for whom these evaluations should be conducted and how the recruitment process should proceed. This still requires a great deal of further development and clarification.

Improvement suggestions:

When drafting a job advertisement, it would be helpful to have a ready-made template that asks for the necessary information, if candidates are to be evaluated on that basis. However, it is important that applying for a position at HAMK does not consist solely of filling in endlessly long forms; the applicant's own voice should also be able to come through in the cover letter and the research plan.

At the application review stage, it must be possible to trust that the Head of the Research Unit responsible for the recruitment knows what kind of person is needed for the team. At this stage, using the criteria framework is too labor-intensive and may also lead to an incorrect selection. If candidates are selected solely on the basis of the criteria, it does not take into account that applicants may have very different types of subject-matter expertise. An applicant may be highly accomplished and suitable according to the criteria, but their research topic may not align with the focus of the research unit.

If and when a tenure track evaluation is to be carried out for the selected candidates before the recruitment is finalized, the recruitment process would be facilitated if the interviewer had a ready-made list of questions that would provide answers to all the items in the tenure track evaluation form.

The tenure track form should be significantly shortened and simplified. Currently, the same questions had to be answered multiple times under different headings. It would be advisable to focus on the main headings and carefully consider the questions related to them. The number of main headings could also be reduced and some of them combined. As it stands, carrying out the evaluation was extremely labor-intensive and partly frustrating. For example, stakeholders were mentioned in several different sections, and it was not always clear which stakeholders were being referred to—sometimes companies, sometimes others.

Which qualitative criteria would you suggest adopting:

This would require more in-depth consideration. It could be developed further together. As I mentioned above, the criteria could partly be combined and shortened. The thematic areas themselves were, in my opinion, well identified and are relevant. What is needed is clarification and simplification. In order for me to respond to this properly, I would need to

go through the criteria carefully. That would require a significant amount of time, which unfortunately I do not have available to devote to this at the moment.

Any other comments:

Internal Pilot

Internal Pilot 1

Personnel responsible:

Researcher Supervisor, HAMK Edu and Innovation research unit.

Recruitment process of the internal candidate? *(How was the candidate chosen for this evaluation process? Did the candidate approach the topic of becoming a Principal Research Scientist? Or was the position recommended to the candidate by the supervisor? etc. Who and how was the evaluation process conducted?)*

Both of these:

The candidate approached the topic of becoming a Principal Research Scientist, and the position was recommended to the candidate by the supervisor

What merits and/or criteria were used to confirm that the internal candidate was competent for the Principal Research Scientist Position?

The new evaluation criteria used at HAMK were used.

Which qualitative researcher evaluation criteria was used? At which stage of the recruitment and/or evaluation process?

The evaluation was done one month prior to the start of the tenure track. The broad set of qualitative criteria in the HAMK template were used.

Feedback:

Positives:

- focus on qualitative criteria
- broad set of different criteria
- clearly formulated criteria

- makes it clear to the applicant and the supervisor what is the current state and which areas should be further developed during the tenure track

Challenges:

- very broad set of criteria – completing the evaluation form was time consuming
- the applicants should be instructed to create their CVs according to the criteria and describe them as concretely as possible
- do all tenure track candidates have a possibility to teach at HAMK, or supervise thesis?

Improvement suggestions:

- “For early career researchers it is understandable to see more sole authored articles.”

I disagree with this statement, I think it’s quite the opposite. Most young researchers do an article-based PhD thesis, and the articles are almost always written with the supervisors/other researchers. I think that later on they have more skills to write sole authored publications:

The description of the criteria ‘**Collaboration within international authorship groups**’ focuses more on sole/multiple author roles, but I think the focus could be more on publications having international collaboration, which I think is more relevant.

This criterion exists twice: **Variation of stakeholders in development projects**

Which qualitative criteria would you suggest adopting:

I think all of them are relevant, but especially activity in funding applications and connections of own research to HAMK other research areas. Also, research networks are important.

Any other comments:

Development Needs

Standard Principal Research Scientist job notification

There is a need to create a standard template for advertising principal research scientist positions. HR also needs to be incorporated into the job notification creation process to ensure the correct procedures are followed, accurate details of the salary are advertised, and contract types are included.

There is also the need to highlight the need for each selected candidate to go through the tenure track evaluation. Each candidate selected during the recruitment needs to undergo a further evaluation to determine if they are competent HAMK principal research scientists or if certain competencies still need to be developed or enhanced in the tenure track process. This evaluation should be conducted regardless of their level of education, or the prestige of the institutions they have worked in.

The tenure track evaluation has implications for the type of contract which is offered to the candidate and on their salary. Thus, it is important to create employment advertisements which disclose this tenure track evaluation, and its impact on prospective contracts and salaries to the candidates.

It is also vital to create standard content which includes the job description, the duties and the roles of Principal research scientists which can be used in job advertisements. Each respective supervisor can add additional details to these job descriptions as needed.

Standard recruitment and evaluation process

The pilots identified that whilst supervisors are responsible for initiating the recruitment process, each supervisor had a different manner of conducting the actual recruitment process. It is important to create a standard recruitment process which all supervisors can follow. However, if needed, certain aspects of the process can be altered, such as adding additional interviews, asking for additional materials and/or including tasks.

The proposal for this process is described below.

- Stage 1- Initial Applications
 - Job advertisement created.
 - Request a modified **TENK CV, a list of publications, research proposal, and a motivational letter.**
 - Initial evaluation of the applications received.

- Stage 2- Invitation to a live/virtual interview
 - Applicants invited to a live/virtual interview.
 - Applicants requested to prepare a **research proposal presentation** (a template provided).
 - Applicants asked to complete a **pre-interview preparation document** (a template provided).
 - Applicants asked to consider their **ideal research proposal.**

- Stage 3- Conducting the interview
 - Applicants are asked to conduct the **research proposal presentation.**

- Discussion of the **pre-interview preparation document**.
 - Applicants asked about their **ideal research proposal**.
 - Applicants asked other important questions as decided by the supervisor.
 - Evaluation conducted and final candidates chosen.
- Stage 4- Tenure track evaluation of chosen candidates
 - A HR representative and the supervisor will conduct a **tenure track evaluation**.
 - The tenure track stage will be confirmed by either the evaluation team and/or the vice rector.
 - Final candidate/s will be offered an employment contract.

It is important that the designated personnel who are involved in the evaluation have access to all of the materials of the candidate and that information from the interviews is also noted down by those conducting them.

All chosen candidates need to be subject to the tenure track evaluation regardless of the researcher career stage, level of education and/or if they are internally or externally recruited.

Important to consider resources and time limitations

Qualitative analysis requires **more time commitment and resources** from those conducting the analysis. This was a common form of feedback from the supervisors who conducted the pilots. It is therefore **important to consider effective tools which evaluators** could use in order to effectively identify the qualitative criteria. The **tools also need to be further supported by the types of materials which are provided by those who are being evaluated**.

The evaluation process needs to thus be built with the new criteria, the new evaluations materials and the tools for conducting the evaluation in consideration. Similarly, it is vital to **ensure that the evaluation process is also not complicated, overwhelming or too resource and time intensive** for those being evaluated. It is also essential that those **being evaluated are able to express themselves in the application process**. Thus, there needs to be a balance between uniformity in the application process and promoting the ability for applicants to highlight their unique value.

In addition, it is important to **consider the types of employment contracts, salaries and career development opportunities** to ensure that the most appropriate candidates apply to HAMK. Receiving high quality applications from high quality researchers is a strategic goal for HAMK, so HAMK also needs to ensure that they provide the conditions needed to attract high

quality researchers. In turn, if HAMK is to offer more demanding contracts and more competitive salaries and career opportunities, the recruitment of new principal research scientists needs to be conducted very carefully. This is why qualitative analysis will become central.

Structure and organization of the criteria

The supervisors who participated in the pilots commented about the **criteria appearing multiple times under different sub-criteria** or competence categories. For example, multi-author publications as a criteria can support publication skills, but also collaboration skills and teamwork skills. In this sense it becomes **difficult to assign the criteria** of multi-author publications to only of the three sub-categories or competences. It is thus important to consider best to organize the sub-categories or competences. Is it more effective to define what skills each criteria supports more rigidly or merely request that evaluators understand the one criterion can support the presence of multiple skills of competence.

Most important and relevant criteria

The supervisors commented that **all of the criteria which have been proposed were useful and relevant in regard to identifying high quality researcher skills, experience and potential**. In particular, the criteria which focused on **funding and network competence were very important**. These have traditionally been used in HAMK to evaluate principal research scientists, however primarily viewed through quantitative means. The qualitative aspects will hopefully provide a more comprehensive understanding of the funding and networking potential and existing competencies of candidates.

In addition, **RDI funding was viewed as needing to be an independent sub-category to help highlight its importance** and weight in the evaluation. The criteria which support not only the current funding competence or experience, but also those skills which support the potential, motivation, activeness and enhancement in funding competence need to be highlighted.

The **relevance of research proposals being relevant, applicable and directly integrated into HAMK's other research areas, strategies and direction** was also highlighted as important. The criteria which focus on identifying the valued added of candidates not only in the immediate researcher role, but how their experience or current research direction supports other agendas of HAMK are very important.

However, the pilot also highlighted the need to determine **which criteria bear more weight** in the recruitment process and to what **extent the recruiting supervisor is responsible** for defining these.